

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd TNA Call Documentation - User

STORIES TNA2 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Development of hybrid carbon/metal oxide supercapacitors
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	HyCMOSC
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	Institute of Emerging Technologies, Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Supercapacitor, carbon material, hybrid supercapacitor, metal oxide
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	September 16 th , 2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	December 15 th , 2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	September 18 th , 2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	December 14 th , 2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	28
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Weekend and travelling days (2)
Number of days using the RI	64
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>This proposal deals with the development of hybrid supercapacitors that combines the characteristic high power of double layer supercapacitors (carbon-based electrodes) with higher energy density pseudocapacitors (metal oxide-based electrodes). The hybrid supercapacitors should present improved performance with respect to double layer capacitors, maintaining its characteristic high-power density.</p>	

The objectives of this proposal include the synthesis of hybrid materials that combines the high surface area and excellent electrical conductivity of carbon materials (such as graphene, carbon nanotubes or carbon fibers) with the higher capacitance of some metal oxides (V₂O₅, WO₃, MnO₂, etc.), that can be nanodispersed on the carbon surface. It will be also pursued to determine the best combination of electrode materials to optimized energy density, power density and cyclability.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The first step after my arrival at the HMU facilities was a meeting with the local group to exchange experiences and research topics and organize the experimental work.

The initial decision was to start working on the deposit of an anode material using Cu as support. Previous to the deposit of metal oxides as anode material, the copper support has to be coated with a carbon layer of graphene oxide or a layer of exfoliated activated carbon.

The main instrument used for the preparation of the samples was a potentiostat-galvanostat that allows the use of different techniques to achieve the deposit of the desired materials. Both potentiostatic and galvanostatic tests were performed depending on the material that is being pursued. To characterize the electrodes prepared, apart from the electrochemical characterizations, SEM was the main tool to control the type of deposit achieved. In addition, it is also intended to use x-ray diffraction to analyze the crystallographic phases obtained.

Some issues were detected when performing carbon depositions on Cu (both with the graphene oxide and the exfoliated activated carbon prepared at INCAR) thus so it was decided to make direct deposition of the different metal oxides onto carbon support to secure some results. The carbon support selected was a Toray carbon paper that presents high electrical conductivity and a relatively high surface area to deposit the metal oxides and it also easy to handle.

The first metal oxide deposited was V₂O₅ (to be used as a cathode material), using as a precursor a 1M solution of VOSO₄. A chronoamperometric technique was used for the electrodeposition fixing a potential of 1.2 V versus Ag/AgCl reference electrode, using various times (ranging between 5-30 min) and different temperatures (from room temperature and 65 °C were tested). The second metal oxide deposited was MoO₃, that is intended to be used as anode material. The precursor used was a 0.07 M solution of Na₂MoO₄ with a pH of 3.2 (adjusted with H₂SO₄). In this case a potentiometric technique was used with a negative current of -5 mA/cm² for times ranging between 5 to 10 min. Some of the samples obtained were post-processed in an oven at 350 °C for 10 hours while others were tested as obtained.

A final metal oxide was MnO₂ (to be used as a cathode material). The precursor selected was an acidic solution (0.1 M H₂SO₄) containing 0.1 M of MnSO₄. The method selected to obtain the precursor was a potentiometric technique with a positive current of 25 mA/cm² with electrodeposition times ranging between 40 to 80 seconds. The obtained electrodes were post-processed at 200 °C for 2 hours in an oven in air.

The electrodes obtained were tested using SEM to observe the shape and type of deposit and analyze the metal content. XRD will be obtained in the next weeks to determine the crystallographic phases present in the deposits. The electrochemical characterization done is, as planned, a 3-electrode characterization using galvanostatic charge/discharge experiments and cycle voltammetry (CV) to analyze the presence of possible redox reactions and/or the pseudocapacitive behavior of the metal oxides deposited on the carbon support.

CVs were performed at different scan rates varying from 1 mV/s to 50 mV/s to analyze the shape of the curves and see the behavior. Equally, the charge/discharge curves were performed at different current densities varying from 1 to 15 mA/mg and different electrochemical parameters

were calculated as specific capacitance, energy efficiency, equivalent series resistance, etc., to be able to compare the properties of the systems obtained.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Promising results were obtained from the electrodeposition of different metal oxides onto a carbon support. Initially Toray carbon paper (TC) was selected due to its properties and its surface was modified by a thermal oxidation in a furnace at 550 °C for 1 hour in order to achieve better wettability. Images of the TC electrode are shown in Figure 1, where rather clean surfaces are observed.

Figure 1: Toray carbon paper electrodes (a) and SEM images of the carbon fibers (b-d).

The deposits of V₂O₅ could not be obtained at room temperature, but were successfully obtained at 65 °C. The amount of deposit was controlled by the deposition time and Figures 2 and 3 show the deposits obtained at 5 and 15 minutes as examples, respectively. In Figure 2 it can be observed that V₂O₅ is grown over the fibres in a rather inhomogeneous way, with some larger particles distributed on the more external part of the electrodes (a) but well attached to the surface (b and c). The fibre surface is covered with a thin layer of metal oxide but it also contains larger knot-shaped particles (c).

Figure 3: Toray carbon paper electrodes with V_2O_5 deposits obtained after 15 minutes of deposition at different magnifications

Deposits of MoO_3 were also obtained and different morphology was observed in the deposits. They form cylinders covering the carbon fibres in a rather homogenous way. Due to differences in expansion coefficients the cylinders are broken after thermal oxidation at 350 °C as shown in Figure 4 where MoO_3 deposits can be observed before and after the thermal treatment.

Figure 4: Toray carbon paper electrodes with MoO_3 deposits obtained after 5 minutes of deposition with (a) as obtained and (b) after oxidation at 350 °C

Deposits obtained after 10 minutes are very similar but thicker as it can be observed in Figure 5. The contact between the metal oxide and the fibre seems to be more mechanical (metal oxide is just grown on top of the carbon fibre but with less chemical interaction that in the case of the V_2O_5).

Figure 5: Toray carbon paper electrodes with MoO_3 deposits thermally oxidized obtained after (a) 5 minutes of deposition and (b) 10 minutes of deposition

The last metal oxide deposited was MnO_2 that yielded a totally different morphology (Figure 6). Rather spherical particles of a few hundred nanometres are found on the surface of the carbon fibres (Figure 6a shows the clean surface of the carbon fibre for comparison). The increase in the deposition time from 20 to 80 second is reflected in the increase on the number of particles but no significant increase in their diameter is observed. It seems convenient to increase the deposition time in future experiment to obtain higher energy densities.

Figure 7: CVs performed on Toray carbon paper electrodes with no material electrodeposited.

Figure 8: CVs performed on Toray carbon paper electrodes after the electrodeposition of V_2O_5 during 30 min.

Figure 9: CVs performed on Toray carbon paper electrodes after the electrodeposition of MoO_3 during 10 min.

Figure 10: CVs performed on Toray carbon paper electrodes after the electrodeposition of MnO_2 during 40 seconds.

Similarly, all the samples produced were analysed using galvanostatic experiments in charge/discharge processes. Experiments were performed at several current densities, ranging from 1 to 15 mA/mg of active material. Only one cycle is showed in the plots, although at least ten were registered at each current density. Figure 11 show the charge discharge cycles for the Toray carbon fibres, that show very low capacitances, as notices for the short time of charge and discharge.

Figure 11: Galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments performed for the Toray carbon fibers.

Figure 12 represents the charge-discharge curves for the electrodeposited V₂O₅ during 10 minutes at 1.2 V. The results obtained for the other V₂O₅ are not showed.

Figure 12: Galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments performed for the electrodeposited V₂O₅s during 10 minutes at 1.2 V.

Figure 13 show the charge-discharge curves for the MO₃ electrodeposited at a current density of 20 mA during 5 minutes. It is worth mentioning the low efficiency showed at low current densities. The tests are performed in negative potential ranges.

Figure 13: Galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments performed for the electrodeposited MoO₃ during 5 minutes at 20 mA.

Finally, Figure 14 shows the charge-discharge curves obtained for the MnO₂ electrodeposited during 40 seconds.

Figure 14: Galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments performed for the electrodeposited MnO₂ during 40 seconds at 100 mA.

The results obtained will be further analysed to obtain conclusion and prepare the 2-e⁻electrode

cell experiments.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

Several important conclusions can be withdrawn from the results obtained during the stay at the HMU facilities. The deposits of carbon materials (graphene oxides and exfoliated activated carbon) on Cu substrate were not satisfactory as little carbon material were deposited and the material is poorly stuck onto the metal surface. The few attempts done onto Aluminium were even more discouraging and no deposit was formed.

The growth of metal oxide was then performed directly onto a carbon support that proved to be suitable for this purpose as shown in the above Figures 1 to Figure 6. The electrochemical results are summarized in Table 1. Toray carbon support shows very little capacitance and it is clear that it only acts as a support. As a general rule it is clearly observed that the formation of larger deposits does no benefit the specific capacitance of the material. As an example, the increase of time from 10 to 30 minutes in the deposition time of V₂O₅ increases the mass loading from 2.2 to 9.4 mg but negatively affects the electrochemical performance. Larges specific capacitances and better coulombic and energetic efficiencies are obtained with less metal oxide deposited.

Exactly the same phenomena are observed with the deposited MoO₃, where an increase of mass loading from 3.4 to 6.8 mg reduce the electrode performance, with lower specific capacitances and worst efficiencies. It is likely that in both cases the thickness of the deposits of metal oxides, with their poor electrical conductivities are responsible of the behaviour observed. In both metal oxides their behaviour at low current densities is very poor, probably due to self-discharge processes.

Finally, the electrodeposit of MnO₂ yields the most promising results giving the highest specific capacitances and very high energy and coulombic efficiencies. That occurs without reaching a full coverage of the carbon surface, being noticeable that in this case the increase in metal oxide deposit from 1.7 to 3.0 mg of deposit does not significantly deteriorates the electrochemical behaviour of the electrode. These results seem to indicate that the electrodeposition method has to be oriented to cover more surface of the carbon surface, but avoiding the MnO₂ growth on previously deposited metal oxide. Using higher surface area carbon might be an excellent idea to continue this research.

Table 1: Data collected for the different electrodeposited metal oxides in a three- electrode cell from the charge-discharge experiments at various current densities.

Toray (580C)					
Masa (mg)	I (mA/mg)	ESR (Ω)	$\epsilon_{\text{eculombica}}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\text{energetica}}$ (%)	C (F/g)
38,0	1	0,0	96,5	85,6	0,013
	2	0,0	98,4	88,7	0,012
	5	0,0	99,3	90,6	0,012
	10	0,0	99,5	91,6	0,012
	15	0,0	99,5	91,9	0,012

Toray MoO ₃ 20mA 10min					
Masa (mg)	I (mA/mg)	ESR (Ω)	$\epsilon_{\text{eculombica}}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\text{energetica}}$ (%)	C (F/g)
7,5	1	---	---	---	---
	2	---	---	---	---
	5	---	---	---	---
	10	1,8	76,6	50,9	0,20
	15	2,1	82,8	61,8	0,20

Toray V2O5 1,2V 10min					
Masa (mg)	I (mA/mg)	ESR (Ω)	$\epsilon_{\text{eculombica}}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\text{energetica}}$ (%)	C (F/g)
2,2	1	0,0	97,6	77,9	58
	2	0,8	98,3	76,7	49
	5	1,2	98,9	75,2	41
	10	0,6	99,0	75,3	73
	15	0,4	99,1	75,5	106

Toray V2O5 1,2V 30min					
Masa (mg)	I (mA/mg)	ESR (Ω)	$\epsilon_{\text{eculombica}}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\text{energetica}}$ (%)	C (F/g)
9,4	1	---	---	---	---
	2	---	---	---	---
	5	0,0	17,1	12,4	34
	10	0,4	53,6	37,4	34
	15	1,3	65,6	43,8	32

Toray MoO ₃ -20mA 5min (350C)					
Masa (mg)	I (mA/mg)	ESR (Ω)	$\epsilon_{\text{eculombica}}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\text{energetica}}$ (%)	C (F/g)
3,4	1	1,4	25,9	15,1	110
	2	1,5	60,3	42,8	95
	5	1,2	81,1	63,5	86
	10	1,5	89,9	73,1	79
	15	1,5	92,7	75,7	73

Toray MoO ₃ -20mA 10min (350C)					
Masa (mg)	I (mA/mg)	ESR (Ω)	$\epsilon_{\text{eculombica}}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\text{energetica}}$ (%)	C (F/g)
6,8	1	---	---	---	---
	2	1,0	25,8	14,5	83
	5	1,8	66,6	48,6	71
	10	1,4	81,2	63,1	64
	15	1,1	86,7	68,9	60

Toray MnO ₂ 100mA 40s (200C)					
Masa (mg)	I (mA/mg)	ESR (Ω)	$\epsilon_{\text{eculombica}}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\text{energetica}}$ (%)	C (F/g)
1,7	1	2,0	103,6	82,9	204
	2	1,5	101,7	84,0	195
	5	1,4	100,7	84,8	186
	10	1,2	100,3	85,2	180
	15	1,2	100,2	85,2	177

Toray MnO ₂ 100mA 80s (200C)					
Masa (mg)	I (mA/mg)	ESR (Ω)	$\epsilon_{\text{eculombica}}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\text{energetica}}$ (%)	C (F/g)
3,00	1	2,1	105,8	81,5	200
	2	2,1	102,9	82,9	188
	5	1,6	101,2	84,3	177
	10	1,4	100,5	83,8	170
	15	---	---	---	---

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The main achievements reached during my stay at the HMU facilities are related with the growth of several metal oxides on a carbon support. These materials are known because of the high specific capacitance that they can show but the experimental preparation method is crucial for their performance. Electrodeposition seems to be adequate for the preparation of these kind of hybrid materials as the performance observed in a three-electrode cells is very promising. It has been established that the covering of the carbon materials (electrically conducting support) has to be maximized but with a limitation of thickness in the oxide film to limit the lost of performance due to the difficulties in electron transfer in the non-conductive metal oxides. Based on the results already obtained MnO₂ yields the best performance with the highest specific capacitance and very promising Energy efficiency (always higher than 80 %). More important is that these results are obtained with a low covering of the carbon surface and the search of an experimental method to increase the covering (avoiding the increase in the thickening of the deposit) might increase further more the capacitance of this hybrid, having a very promising cathode electrode.

The detailed electrochemical characterization and the search of the best possible hybrid devices that will continue at INCAR will indicate the possibility to search for new synthesis routes for the hybrid electrode materials.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

Some of the techniques initially proposed to obtain the hybrid materials were not available during my stay alternatively electrodeposition has been proved as a very suitable technique to the same end that has yielded very promising results.

Some other characterization techniques like (X-ray diffraction) were temporarily out of order and the analysis will be done shortly.

Some experimental difficulties arose when graphene oxides and exfoliated activated carbon were intended to be deposited on a Cu support. The use of Cu limits the potential range of stability of the electrode (due to the hydrogen evolution reaction in negative potentials and the copper oxidation at the positive ones) and the bonding of carbon on top of the metal was weak. This problem was solved using a carbon support instead of a metal one.

Apart from these technical issues, the cooperation has been very fluent and the two groups involved are planning to continue with a future collaboration signing a cooperation agreement between the two institutions.

Equipment not accessible:

X-ray diffractometer temporarily out of order.

CVD equipment was not fully operative yet.

Intended publications

The work done is still in a very initial stage and the number of publications cannot be fully defined. For sure one publication will be released on the topic but it might be possible to release a number of publications once the pending results are achieved:

Publication 1: Asymmetric cells can be built using two different metal oxides supported on carbon. For example, a $\text{MO}_3//\text{MnO}_2$ cell might work with the MoO_3 in the negative electrode and the MnO_2 in the positive one, but it is still necessary to optimize selected support.

Publication 2: Hybrid cell containing a metal oxide in one of the electrodes and a double layer-based electrode containing a high surface area carbon. Here, it is necessary to optimize the carbon support for the metal oxide (preferably a high area carbon instead of the Toray carbon paper that can increase the load and the dispersion of the metal oxide. The most promising result obtained in these early experiments are the ones obtained with MnO_2 .

The most likely journal to publish the results are: The Journal of Power Sources, Electrochimica Acta, Batteries and Supercaps, etc. but the final decision will depend on the results obtained.

Data management

The obtained data will be stored in SACO which is a corporate CSIC cloud and it will be shared by the two research groups involved in this proposal. Once the pending experiments are finished they will be published in open access and they will also be stored in the CSIC public repository (<https://digital.csic.es/>)

Conclusions / additional comments

The work done during this period of three months has allowed to start a collaboration between two European research groups with different but complementary expertise. This collaboration is

likely to continue in the future with exchange of students and cooperation in future European projects and a cooperation agreement between the two institution is under study. During my stay I participate as a speaker in one of The Athena Talks organized by the HMU entitled: Carbon Materials for Energy Storage. Also a internal seminar with the host research group was organized to share the electrochemical techniques as cells that are used at iNCAR's group. The experimental results are still incipient but promising. Three different metal oxides have been successfully synthesized on a carbon support and their electrochemical properties in three-electrode cells have been tested. More studies are necessary to optimize the carbon support and the amount/morphology of the metal oxide deposited. In the next weeks several hybrid two electrode cells will be studied at INCAR to analyze their potential performance in terms of capacitance and energy/power densities.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment]

Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment]

Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics

Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. Yes No

[Please specify any problems]

RI extension / upgrades required

In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation.

Yes No

[Please specify]

Problems with local regulations	<p>Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<i>[Please specify]</i>	
Health and safety issues	<p>Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	<p>Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	<p>Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environmental issues	<p>Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details.</p>

	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify				
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
<i>[Please provide suggestions for specific type of facilities missing (RI gaps) or measurement / experiments you would like to perform which cannot be done on current StoRIES facilities]</i>					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
<i>[Your suggestions]</i>					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES.				
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>					
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support?				
	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Please provide details]

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

